

AN APPRAISAL OF THE IMPACT OF CORRUPTION ON SUSTAINABLE
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA

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**AN APPRAISAL OF THE IMPACT OF CORRUPTION ON SUSTANIABLE
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA
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Abstract

The paper examines the impact of corruption on sustainable industrial development in Nigeria. It went further to access Nigeria's industrial sector of the economy and the constraint militating against effective industrial; development. Corruption has become anthemia in the contemporary world, which resulted into a global concern with a debilitating effect on industrial growth and development of several nations of the world, especially underdeveloped and developing countries. World Bank (1997) has described corruption as the abuse of public office through the instrumentality of private agent who actively offers bribes to circumvent public policies and processes for competitive advantage and profit.

Beyond bribery, public office can also be abuse for personal benefit though patronage and nepotism, for example, the theft of state asset or diversion of state revenues. The paper analyze the effect of corruption on economic development in Nigeria. It reviews consequences of corruption and the various anti-corruption measures taken by the government. It also suggests that government should formulate corruption preventive mechanism, policies and build institutions like what we have in China and Indonesia. The government should push forward the corruption prevention work more forcefully and place it on a more solid legal framework. The paper concludes that corruption if not abated will constitute a clog to Nigeria development. The paper went further to canvas a holistic approach to solving the problem of corruption as a panacea for a robust, sustainable economic development and growth in Nigeria

Key words: Corruption. Development. Industrialization. Sustainability, Globalization.

INTRODUCTION

The word, corruption, is derived from the Latin word "corruptus" meaning 'improper, illicit, immoral, vivious, bribable, venal and so on.' According to the Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English, 'Corruption' means 'dishonest, illegal or immoral behavior especially from someone with power.' It can be defined as an "impairment of integrity" and "inducement to wrong by improper and unlawful means." Corruption has broadly been defined as a perversion or a change

from good to bad. Specifically, corruption or corrupt behavior involves the violation of established rules for personal gain and profit (Sen 1999).

Corruption is efforts to secure wealth or power through illegal means; private gain at public expense; or a misuse of public power for private benefit Lipset & Lenz, 2000. Corruption is a vice which is international scope, monstrous in nature, crudely rampant in developing economics and unobstructively devastating and pervasive in virtually all Less Developed Counties (LDC) of world. Corruption is not pervasive, alarming endemic in Nigeria but according to Achebe (1983), the vice has entered the fatal state in the country.

Conceptual Framework according to Nye, "Corruption is a deviation from the formal duties of a public role because of private-regarding (personal, close family, private clique) pecuniary exercise of certain types of private regarding influence. This includes such behaviors as bribery (use of reward to pervert the judgment of a person in position of trust); nepotism (appointment by reason of ascriptive relation rather than merit), and misappropriation (illegal appropriation of public resources for private regarding uses)" Corruption may include bribery: abuse or misuse of office; illegal payments; kickbacks; tax, credit and customs fraud; misappropriation and embezzlement; currency violations; forgery; false accounting; real estate swindles and land speculation; smuggling; over-invoicing; over-pricing; hoarding; illegal flight of capital, fraudulent sales etc. (Aluko, 2006).

According to Lateef Adegbite, corruption is define as "the act of turning power and authority into ready cash. Shehu Musa defines corruption ad 'the diversion of resources from the betterment of the community to the gain of individuals at the expense of the community'.

The United Nations Organization also has the following to say about corruption:

Through experience, observation, information discussions, reports, newspapers, findings of commissions of inquiry and of limited social-scientific studies, one can make an endless descriptive list of instances of corrupt conduct or practices. One can also give these various instances assorted labels: bribery; abuse and or misuse of office; illegal payments; kickbacks; tax, credit, and customs fraud; misappropriation and embezzlement; currency violations; forgery; false accounting; real estate swindles and land speculation; abuse of public grants; environmental damage; smuggling; violation of labour regulations; over-invoicing, over-pricing and transfer-pricing; illegal/illegitimate monopolization, and restraints of trade; hoarding; illegal flight of capital; exploitation of labour; fraudulent sales; adulterated food or hazardous drugs; acts of constraint or distortion of development plans, etc. Labanji Bolaji's definition sees corruption as "The act of money-giving and money-taking to induce the receiver to carry out an action in favor of the giver who is not in fact entitled to the benefit of that action".

Bardhan (1997) defined public sector corruption as "the use of public office for private gains." The understanding here is that the private gain imbroglio is either in cash or in kind and, could be for one's own benefits, one's own family's or one's own personal friends. Essentially, this means that corruption is much more than meets the eyes. It includes everything that is capable of scandalizing or debasing us and making us morally bankrupt, ranging from fornication and adultery to lasciviousness and sexual harassment.

But (Moodie, 1980) argued that corruption and scandal are not synonymous and, that we may find either in the absence of the other. But even at that, it is appropriately understandable that those situational elements or components capable of morally debasing us, are all constituting the congruent of corruption.

Garner (2004:4) defined corruption as "depravity, perversion, or taint; an impairment of integrity, virtue, or moral principle; especially, the impairment of a public official's duties by bribery.' It is the act of doing something with an intent to give some advantage inconsistent with official duty and the rights of others; a fiduciary's or official's use of a station or office to procure some benefit either personally or for someone else, contrary to the rights of others. If this definition is anything to go by and also assessing it from the legal point of view, it means that no-body in this universe is above corruption. It means that everybody in this universe (without any exception) is corrupt since at one time or the other we all have used or various offices to procure some benefit either personally or for someone else, contrary to the rights of others. Corruption is an issue, which many people have tried to define across a variety of situations that suits their whims and caprices, but failed to accomplish anything in terms of its development and containment. For Perkins and Boyce (1982:2), the word corruption indicates "impurity or debasement and when found in the criminal law it means depravity or gross impropriety." There have been different views and concepts about all that corruption really embraces and, there will continue to be expressed more divergent views on this controversial topic depending on how strongly the proponent views it. In the words of Bollens and Schmandt (1979:17), as most definitions indicate, two general types of corruption can be identified: "those in which public office is used to enhance the wealth or pleasure of the occupant; and those in which it is employed to maintain or expand the holder's personal power. Acts of bribery, kickbacks, influence peddling, and conflict of interests come under the first classification, while election frauds, "dirty tricks," illegal campaign contributions, and the abuse of administrative authority fall into the second category. Sexual favors, a form of political corruption that has received considerable notoriety in recent years, may be placed in either classification depending on whether their use is for personal pleasure of the office holder or for gaining influence over others.

For Mwaffisi (1999:1), corruption involves "the payment of bribe, that is money or material items offered to provide (often illegal or dishonest) services or decision in favour of a giver." He went further to categorize corruption into two levels. There are those who engage in petty corruption that is those who receive bribes as a supplement to their meager income. This is referred to as petty corruption and involves individuals being forced to pay small amounts of money in order to get the service that they deserve to get free or with a little payment. On the other hand, there are those who engage in grand corruption because of greed. In the health sector, this involves the payment of big sums of money by rich individuals and institutions to some corrupt government officials in order to win tenders for the supply of pharmaceuticals, medical equipment and supplies.

The Nature and Characteristics of Corruption

Five different types of corruption are easily identifiable. These are political, economic, bureaucratic, judicial and moral corruption. At the global plane, nine different types of corruption have been identified.

A typology of corruption

Type	Status of Main Perpetrators	Enabling Means	Usual Motive	Victims
I POLITICAL	*Chief executives *Other political office holders	* Political power *Economic power *Social power	*To gain or retain political power to victimize opponents	*Ideals and values of the polity
ECONOMIC COMMERCIAL	Businessmen *Contractors *Consultants	Economic Power *Socio-political connections	*To make more profit	*Generality of tax payers and other citizens
ADMIN/ PROFESSIONAL *Material wealth	*Highly placed civil servants and executives of parastatals	*Administrative authority *Technicality and exclusivity *Professionals: Lawyers, doctors, engineers, university teachers	*Cultivation of political and social connections	* Generality of tax payers and other citizens *Consumers of services *Other professionals
IV ORGANIZED	*Political, economic, social and bureaucratic elites *High echelons of control agencies	*Influential connections to information sources *Control and enforcement authority	*Money and material wealth	*Government treasury *Private professionals
WORKING CLASS	*Artisans * Junior and intermediate staff	*Technical or occupational skills	*Money and material wealth	*Consumers of goods and services

	*Market men and women	*Ignorance, carelessness and acquiescence on the part of the public		
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Sources: Culled from Kalu and Osibajo, 99

Specific Factors Responsible for Corruption in Nigeria

In this work we will consider the following factors, which have been identified as responsible for corruption in Nigeria. These are:

- i. The spoils system and nepotism
- ii. Social values
- iii. The long stay of the military in power
- iv. The communal culture of Africa
- v. Economic factors
- vi. Political factors
- vii. Officials' ignorance of rules and regulations
- viii. The citizenry's ignorance of their civic rights.
- ix. Apathy on the part of many citizens
- x. Religious factors

Government Documents

Adamawa State Local Government Service Commission: Progress Report from the State presented or the meeting of officials responsible for Local Government Affairs of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. 31 July to 2 August 1996.

Abia State Local Government Service Commission. Annual Report, 1995.

Federal Republic of Nigeria. Model Financial Memoranda for Local Government, 2nd ed. Hazz Printing, Kaduna, 1991.

Imo State Local Government Service Commission for the meeting of officials responsible for Local Government Affairs in the Federation.

Kwara State Local Government Service Commission: Progress Report from Kwara State presented at the meeting of the Key Functionaries Responsible for Local Government Affairs in the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 24-27 June 1997.

STRATEGIES TO COMBAT CORRUPTION IN NIGERIA

Adefila (2004) classifies measures aimed at checking corruption into two namely: governmental, and management. He itemized governmental measures to include improved conditions of service, good governance, adequate punishment for the corrupt workers, provision of basic social amenities, and implementation of a good retirement plan for workers.

Management measures encompass sound internal control system, staff motivation, accountability, and filling organizational positions with only honest workers. In this context, officials and employees at the various levels of government, who manage the public resources allocated for government programmes, have the obligation to render a full account of their activities to the public. Allied to this principle is the need to practice compulsory competitive tendering principle in the award of government contract. This will make our contract prices to be fair and devoid of inflated inputs.

Selection of good employees is critical to good management profile in the workplace. It is pertinent to note that the manager should be a leader in all ramifications of the term, and should be knowledgeable in the subject matter of his specialization in order to be effective in checking corruption and irregularities. He should be incorruptible and lead by example. In his selection process therefore, appropriate screening steps should include reference checks on the curriculum vitae, handwriting and/or finger printing tests depending on the nature of the job, and in-depth interview which may be combined with a written honesty test. Proper training and orientation, of a continuous nature, should also be given to employees upon assumption of office.

THE INFLUENCE OF ANTI-CORRUPTION AGENCIES

Among the measures put in place in curbing corruption, is the establishment of anti-corruption agencies both at the national and global levels.

- i. National Anti-Corruption Agencies - Perhaps the greatest challenge facing the anti-graft agencies at the national level is that of transparency. Cognate to this attribute are the requirements for

credibility, integrity, and effectiveness, among others. The foregoing are ably summarized by Pope and Vog (2000) as follows:

"a test for a government establishing an anticorruption agency is whether it would find the agency's actions acceptable if it were the political opposition rather than the party in power. An enduring formula, which seems fair and workable to everyone, whether in or out of government, needs to be found. This requires, for example, that the agency have significant powers of investigation, prosecution, and deterrence, independent of political parties and government leaders. Accountability is critical to the agency's success, as are checks on its power and the method used for selecting its leadership. Anticorruption agencies will fail if they can be subjected to political direction and used as a weapon to attack critics of the government.

Safeguards have to exist as well, to ensure the agency does not itself become a source for extortion and corruption.' The work of two anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria cannot be underestimated in the war against corruption. These are the Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), and the Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC). It is often said in the lighter mood that the fear of the EFCC, is the beginning of financial prudence.

ii. Global Anti-Corruption Activities

Burton (1999) commenting on global anti-corruption activities, mentions a number of significant international and regional initiatives devoted to fraud control, while however admitting that primary responsibility for tackling corruption and strengthening governance lies within the country concerned. He refers to such efforts as follows:

- the United Nations General Assembly's adoption in 1996 of an International Code of conduct for Public Officials and a declaration against Corruption and Bribery in International Commercial Transactions.
- The IMF's publication of anti-corruption guidelines and confirmation of its readiness to take account of relevant governance issues including corruption when reviewing economic programmes and policies of its members.
- The British Government's support and active participation in anti-corruption initiatives, especially her signing of the European Convention on Corruption and the OECD convention on Combating Bribery in International Business Transactions, and
- Nigeria's membership and participation in the activities of Transparency International.

Among the global anti-corruption activities is Hong Kong SAR's clear, strict Prevention of Bribery Ordinance and strong Independent Commission Against Corruption, which has impressive legal powers and staff of about 1,350 professionals (Pope and Vogl, 2000)

CONCLUSION

Attempts have been made in this paper to examine the various elements of the cankerworm known as corruption. Its various contextual dimensions, among interacting variables, make it rather difficult to define its meaning. Its adverse effect on our socio-economic life cannot however be over-emphasized. These are in the form of crippling levels of poverty, higher prices and fewer job opportunities, reduced productive investment, health, education, and social facilities, and so on.

From the existing literature, one can see that corruption exists at all levels of Nigerian institutions and organization both at private and public services and that corruption if not abated will damage the Nigerian economy. To foster economic growth and development there is the need to transform our national mindset and the government should formulate a comprehensive and sustained economy system which will enhance effective and efficient public and private accountability

REFERENCES

- Adefila, J.J. (2004) Public Servants' Perception of the causes of fraud - A Case Study of Kwara State Public Service. Babcock Journal of Management and Social Sciences. Vol.3 No. 1, Sept. 2004
- Adewunmi W. (1999) Professionalism and Ethics in Banking. Management in Nigeria Vol. 35, No. 1, Jan. -Kim 1999
- Agbaje, E.B.A. (2004) Corruption, Accountability and Good Governance - Reflections on governance in Nigeria's fourth Republic 1999 - 2003. International Review of Politics and Development. Vol. 2, No. 2, June 2004.
- Aluko J (2006) Corruption in the local Government System in Nigeria Ibadan Books Printers
- Adefila J.J (2004) Public Servants' Perspective of the Cause of Fraud -A case Study of Kwara State Public service. Babcock Journal of Management and social Science vol. 3 no. 1, Sept 2004. vol. 35, No. 1. Jan -June 1999.
- Anya, O.A (2000), Privatization in Nigeria, at the Netherlands Congress Centre, The Hague, as part of the independence Day Celebration by the Nigeria embassy at the Hague, September 28. Corruption in Nigeria: Editorial Page ,Washington post 05/03/2005.
- Burton G. (1999) "Global Anticorruption Activities" Management in Nigeria. Vol. 35, No. 1, NIM Jan - Jun. Lagos.
- Bello - Iman I.B (2005). The war against Corruption in Nigeria, problems and prospects. College press and publishers. Ibadan.
- Bolaji lansany, (1970) Anatomy of Corruption in Nigeria, Daysten Press. Ibadan.
- Bardan (1997), "The Role of Governance in Economic development: A Political Economy Approach," OECD Development Centre, Paris.
- Bollens, J.C and Schmandt, H.J., "Political corruption Power, Money and Sex ," U.S.A: Palisade Publishers.
- Bardhan, P. (1997), Corruption and Development ! A Review of Issues , journal of economic literature ,vol 35 pp. 1320-1346
- Burton G (1999)" Global anticorruption activities" Management In Nigeria Vol. 35, No. 1, NIM, Jan -Jun. Lagos.
- Dike, V.E. (2002). The State of education in Nigeria and the health of the nation in the Nigeria Economic Summit Group (NESG) periodical, June 2002. Also see Online Publication, Africa Economic Analysis, at www.afibis.com/analysis/education/10204234737.htm
- Dike, V. "Corruption in Nigeria: A new Paradigm for Effective control" <http://www.Africaneconomicallysis.org/article/gen/corruption/htm.html> accessed on 23/04/06.
- EFCC reports (2005). Effect of Corruption on Nigeria's Economy. Nigeria EFCC Information Communication Technology Department. Abuja
- Gupta, S., H. Davoodi, and R. Alonso -Terme (1998), Does Corruption Affect Income Inequality and Poverty ?", Washington D.C. ",IMF Working Paper WP/98/76, IMF
- Garner, B.A.(2004) "Black's Law Dictionary, 8* ed., U.S.A: Thompson West Publishers Co.
- Gouide and Stasavage (1997)," Corruption: The Issues, Technical Paper No. 122, Produced as part of the research programme on Political Economy and development in Africa.

- I.C.P.C (2006). Nigeria and Corruption. Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences Commission
- Kennish J. W. (1988) "Prevention Starts from the Top" Issues in Security management. Butterworths, Boston
- Klitgaard, R. (2000). Subverting Corruption. Finance and Development. I.M.F June 2000
- Kolade, C. (1999) Working for Business Integrity in Nigeria: The Role of the Professional. Management In Nigeria. Vol. 35, No. 1 Jan - Jun 1999
- Kaufmann, D. and Colleagues. O. (2005). 'Nigeria in Numbers - the Governance Dimension: a preliminary and brief review of recent trends on governance and corruption. Presentation for the President of Nigeria and his Economic Management Team, mimeo.
- Kaufman, D., A Kraay, and M. Mustruzzi (2008), Governance Matter VII: Aggregate and Individual Governance Indicator, 1996-2007, Policy Research working Paper 4654, Word Bank Washington, D.C.
- Kaufmann, D. (2004), " Corruption, Governance and Security: Challenges for the Rich Countries and the world <<http://www.worldbank.org/wbi/governance /pubs/gar2004.html>>.
- Lipset S.M and Les G.S. (2000) Corruption, Culture and Market, in Culture Matters, Lawrence E. Harrison and Samuel Hinghington eds. new York, Basic Books, P112.
- Lateef Adegbite Towards the eradication of a corrupt free society. The role and duties of citizenry p. 152. in perspective on corruption and other Economic crimes in Nigeria, Awa U.Kalu and Yemi Osibayo eds (federal Ministry of Justice review series No2, Fabog Nig Enterprises, Lagos 1991.
- Leite, C. and J. Weidmann (1999) Does Mother Nature Corruption? Natural Resources, Corruption, and Economic Growth, IMF working Paper WP/99/85,IMF, Washington DC.
- Moodie G.C (1980), "On Political Scandals and Corruption, Government and Opposition 15: 208-222.
- Mauro (1995) "Corruption and Growth." Quarterly Journal of Economics 110:681-712.
- Nye, J.S. (1967), Corruption and Political Development: A cost –Benefit Analysis, in the American Political Science review, vol. LXI (61) No.2000. Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala CP' 81 (2006)<<http://alum.mit.edu/ne/noteworthy/news- features/iweala.html>>accessed on may 5,2006.
- Ngozi Okonjo-Iweala <<http://www.worldbank.org>>,accessed on may 5,2006.
- Obasanjo, O.(2004) "Tackling Corruption and Promoting Transparency and Accountability" National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy. National Planning commission, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Olujobi A.O.(1999) Employee Theft: A veritable threat to corporate Survival. Management In Nigeria. VOL. 35, No. 1 Jan-Jun 1999.
- Obasanjo, O. (2004) "Tackling Corruption and Promoting Transparency and Accountability" National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy. National Planning Commission, Abuja, Nigeria.
- Olujobi A. O. (1999) employee Theft: A Veritable Threat to Corporate Survival. Management In Nigeria. Vol. 35, No. 1, Jan - Jun 1999.
- Okonjo-weala, N (2005), Managing the Challenges of Economic Reform in a Global Context: The Case of Nigeria. Global Economic Governance Programme Annual Lecturer 27 May 2005,

University College Oxford Oyediji Ademola (2008) Corruption and Development: A Nigeria Perspective ;
ICAN Journal, Oct/Dec (2008)", Vol. 41 No. 4 Page 38-42
Pope , and Vogl F. (2000) Making Anticorruption Agencies More Effective,
Finance and Development IMF June 2000.
Pope J, and vogl F. (2000) Making Anticorruption Agencies More Effective Finance and
development IMF June 2000.
Perkins and Boyce (1982) Criminal Law 855,3 ed, Cited in Garner, B.A. (2004) "Black's Law
Dictionary, 8th ed., U.S.A: Thompson West Publisher Co.
Ribadu, M. N, (2006). Nigeria's Struggle with Corruption. A paper presented to US Congressional
House Committee on International Development, Washington, DC on 18 May 2006.
Ribadu, M. N. (2004). "Corruption costs Nigeria 40 percent of oil wealth" Retrieved from
http://www.boston.com/news/world/africa/articles/2004/12/17/corruption_co
st_nigeria40percentof oil wealth official sayss? Mode=PF
Sen. A. (1999) Development as Freedom, New York, Anchor books. P.275
Tanzi, V. (1998), "Corruption Around the world: Causes, consequences ,Scope and Cures" ', IMF Working Paper
WP/98/93, IMF, Washington D.C.